

Studies on Dithiocarbamates : Part IX: Kinetic Studies on the Mechanism of Hydrolysis of Azorhodanines

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Effect of temperature on the alkaline (*pH* 10.0) hydrolyses of some *para*- and *ortho*-substituted 5-phenylazorhodanines are reported. For the *para*-substituted compounds, observed rates are well correlated by $\sigma^+\rho$ relation ($\rho = 0.468$) but sign and magnitude of ρ are unaffected by temperature variation. Calculated activation parameters suggest that ΔG^* is nearly invariant, and ΔH^* and ΔS^* show isokinetic relation ship. Results strongly indicate water attack on the solvated anion. For the *ortho*-derivatives, internal strain causes steric assistance in hydrolyses.

Earlier work¹ showed that the rates of alkaline hydrolysis of a series of azorhodanines could not be correlated with Hammett σ constants², but relatively better fit of data could be obtained with Taft σ_R ($\sigma_R = \sigma_p - \sigma'$) values³. Further, *pH*-independent behaviour at fairly strong alkaline medium (*pH* ≥ 10.0) coupled with *pK_a* values and shift in λ_{max} broadly indicated the rate determining formation of a transition state which is largely anionic in character.

The object of the present communication is to provide additional support to the suggested hydrolytic decomposition of these compounds from a study of activation parameters which usually show sufficient sensitivity to substituent polarity². Kinetic behaviour of some typical *ortho*-derivatives have also been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

The appropriate azorhodanines were available to us from our previous studies⁴. The stock solutions were made in acetone-free methanol (BDH) and these were again suitably diluted with methanol so that after mixing with buffer (borate⁵, *pH* = 10.0; $\mu = \sim 0.1$) the

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2. J. E. Leffler and E. Grunwald, *Rates and Equilibria of Organic Reactions*, John Wiley and Sons, New York, N.Y., 1963.
3. R. W. Taft in *Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry*, Ed. by M. S. Newman, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1956, Chap. 13, p. 595.
4. P. B. Talukdar and S. K. Sengupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 291.
5. A. I. Vogel, *A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis*, Longmans, Green and Co., 1959, p. 870.

optical densities were around unity. In the final solutions, proportion of methanol to buffer was always kept at a constant ratio of 40 : 60 (v/v).

Optical densities were measured in a Hilger UVISPEK spectrophotometer using 1 cm. matched quartz cells.

Kinetic Measurements: The sample solution and the buffer were equilibrated at appropriate temperature in a thermostatic bath. The solutions were quickly mixed and the samples were drawn at regular intervals to measure o.d. at 490 m μ (λ_{\max} at pH 10.0). For the *p*-NO₂ derivative measurements were carried out at 520 m μ . Runs were followed until the solutions were nearly colourless or faintly coloured indicating at least 80% completion of reactions. Bath-temperature was maintained constant to within $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

The apparent rate constants were calculated from the slopes of the first-order plots of log₁₀ (o.d.) vs. time which invariably produced excellent straight line upto the last reading indicating absence of interference from reaction products. For the ortho-substituted compounds, rate studies were limited to 25° only since rates were too fast to be measured at higher temperature. The measured rate-constants were all accurate to within $\pm 2\%$ by agreement between duplicate experiments.

The activation parameters (*Ea*, ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔG^* at 25°) were calculated from suitable Arrhenius plots and appropriate equations⁶ for these quantities. The uncertainties in rate constants correspond to uncertainties in *Ea* and ΔH^* of 0.4 to 0.5 Kcal/mole and in ΔS^* of 0.9 entropy unit.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Para-substituted compounds: The *pK_a* values¹ of azorhodanines are around 8, consequently the compounds are reasonably expected to exist in one form (anionic) at pH ≥ 10 , and hence complications arising from several structural species could be kept at minimum and the kinetic results would be more amenable to interpretation. Similarly, the type of polar substituent on 5-arylozo moiety in I are restricted to those whose substituent parameters² (σ values) are fairly well-established. Results of kinetic studies at various temperatures at a fixed pH are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1

Pseudo first order rate constants at different temperatures and at pH 10.0

Substituent	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ per sec.					Relative rates <i>k/k_H</i> (25°)	σ^+ or <i>E_s</i>
	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°		
H	1.313	2.399	4.133	6.908	11.190	1.000	0.000
<i>p</i> -MeO	0.404	0.681	1.228		3.453	0.308	-0.778
<i>p</i> -Me	0.840	1.468	2.559		7.153	0.640	-0.311
<i>p</i> -Cl	0.996	1.739	3.070		7.823	0.758	0.114
<i>p</i> -Br	1.097	1.919	3.262		8.636	0.835	0.150
<i>p</i> -I	1.199	2.149	3.563		9.383	0.913	0.135
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	2.399	3.838	6.908	9.979	—	1.827	0.790
<i>o</i> -MeO	6.774						0.99
<i>o</i> -Me	4.606						0.00
<i>o</i> -Cl	5.066						0.18
<i>o</i> -Br	4.752						0.00
<i>o</i> -I	3.290						-0.20

6. Y. Tanaka, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, **32**, 2405

TABLE 2

Activation parameters for hydrolyses of azorhodanines

Substituent in I _R	E _a Kcal/mole	ΔG* 25° Kcal/mole	ΔH* Kcal/mole	ΔS* cal/deg/mole
H	19.41	22.77	18.82	-13.25
<i>p</i> -MeO	19.83	23.46	19.24	-14.16
<i>p</i> -Me	20.33	23.03	19.74	-11.04
<i>p</i> -Cl	19.79	22.93	19.20	-12.51
<i>p</i> -Br	19.83	22.83	19.24	-12.22
<i>p</i> -I	19.27	22.82	18.68	-13.90
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	18.33	22.42	17.71	-15.81

Inspection of results in Table 1 clearly shows that the substituents exert some influence on the rates of hydrolysis, but the magnitude of variation is not as wide as it could have been for similarly substituted esters⁷ or amides⁸ of benzoic acid. For instance, rate acceleration for the *p*-NO₂ derivative is only five-fold compared to the *p*-MeO-derivative. Previously we have discussed¹ that the anion(II) could possibly stabilise itself through charge delocalisation. In spite of this situation, results suggest that the substituent influence is sufficiently *weak* and apparently does not cause any change in the nature of the reactant; consequently, the mode of fission of the anion through solvent attack is anticipated to be similar in all cases. If this is correct, then $\log k_{T_1}$ vs. $\log k_{T_2}$ should provide a straight line according to the prescription of Exner⁹. This was indeed found to be the case as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Exner type plot of logarithm of rate constants at two different temperatures. Numbers correspond to compds. in Table 1.

7. A. A. Humffray and J. J. Ryan, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1967, 468; refs. cited there.

8. M. Bender, *Chem. Rev.*, 1960, **60**, 50.

9. O. Exner, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1964, **29**, 1094.

Another indication for the nature of the transition state comes from the lack of correlation¹⁰ between rate constants and Hammett σ values and this is similar to our previous experience¹. However, the linear trend improves by the use of Taft σ_R ($\sigma_R = \sigma_p - \sigma'$) parameters indicating that transmission of substituent-effect under the given condition mainly involves polarisation of the intervening conjugated system, But the best fit was found with σ^+ values¹¹ ($\rho = 0.468$, $r = 0.95$, $s = 0.0074$ at 25°). as shown in Fig. 2. At any

Fig. 2. Linear relation between $\log k$ against σ^+ values at 25° and 35° . Numbers correspond to compds. in Table 1.

rate, magnitude and sign of ρ remain fairly steady over the entire range of temperature using either σ_R or σ^+ . This is consistent with a transition state where opportunity for conjugation with substituent is not much greater in the transition state than in the reactant⁷. By implication, the transition state is more like a reactant rather than a product.

From the above considerations, alkaline decomposition of the azorhodanine may be reconciled by assuming passage of the solvated ion (A) to the transition state (complex) through the participation of a solvent molecule causing fission of the rhodanine ring to fragments (C) and (D). This is analogous to the hydrolytic decomposition of arylidene rhodanines¹². This view is also consistent with the isolation of thiooxalic phenylhydrazide

10. R. K. Chaturvedi and E. H. Cordes, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 1232.

11. H. C. Brown and Y. Okamoto, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4979.

12. F. C. Brown, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, **61**, 463.

(C) by Grischuk and Baranov¹³. Fragmentation of rhodanine and its derivative to isothiocyanate intermediate (D) is well documented^{12,14}. At any event, the nature of the primary decomposition products and their subsequent changes, as in the case of (D)₂, do not alter the kinetics of azo-colour disappearance because the products do not show any absorption band around 490 m μ .

The above reasoning could be justified from a consideration of the activation parameters (Table 2). Thus, while ΔG^* values are nearly invariant, the corresponding variation in ΔH^* and ΔS^* are certainly beyond experimental errors. The nature of the variation in ΔH^* and ΔS^* is suggestive of the fact that the overall rates are largely governed by co-operative efforts² (i.e., ΔH^* and $T\Delta S^*$ are of opposite signs). Analogous situation has been encountered in the alkaline hydrolysis of substituted benzamides¹⁵.

Again, Leffler-type¹⁶ plot of ΔH^* vs. ΔS^* undoubtedly shows a good linear trend with all the compounds except the *p*-MeO derivative. Regression analysis of $\delta\Delta H^*$ vs $\delta\Delta S^*$ for all the compounds (including *p*-MeO derivative) provided an isokinetic temperature of 357°K, with $r = 0.884$ and $s = 0.323$. However, the results could be significantly improved when activation parameters are analysed in terms of Hepler's theory¹⁷ where substituent induced changes in enthalpy ($\delta\Delta H^*$) and in entropy ($\delta\Delta S^*$) are considered to be the sum of *internal* and *external* components, such as

$$\delta\Delta H^* = \delta\Delta H_I^* + \delta\Delta H_E^* \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\delta\Delta S^* = \delta\Delta S_I^* + \delta\Delta S_E^* \quad \dots (2)$$

Internal contributions arise from electronic changes within the molecule whereas external changes are concerned primarily with solute-solvent interactions. But internal entropy changes are usually very small^{18,19} in comparison to that induced through solvation interaction mechanism, hence

$$\delta\Delta S^* \approx \delta\Delta S_E^*$$

Again, $\delta\Delta H_E^* = \beta \delta\Delta S^*$ since external component of enthalpy change is accompanied by an entropy change.

The linear relationship between $\delta\Delta H^*$ and $\delta\Delta S^*$ may therefore be expressed as,

$$\delta\Delta H^* - \delta\Delta H_I^* = \beta \delta\Delta S^*$$

or

$$\delta\Delta H^* + 2.303 RT \sigma + \rho = \beta \delta\Delta S^* \quad \dots (3)$$

Using the previously derived value of $\rho(0.468)$, plot of left hand side of equation (3) against $\delta\Delta S^*$ yielded a straight line with $\beta = 307^\circ \text{K}$, $r = 0.985$ and $s = 0.007$. Thus, $\delta\Delta H_I^*$ indeed contributes significantly towards the observed changes in enthalpy and

13. A. P. Grischuk and S. N. Baranov, *Zhur. Obschei Khim.*, 1958, **28**, 896; 1959, **29**, 3329.

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15. I. Meloche and K. J. Laidler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **73**, 1712.

16. (a) J. E. Leffler, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, **20**, 1202;

(b) P. R. Wells, *Chem. Rev.*, 1963, **63**, 171.

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19. C. G. Mitton and R. L. Schowen M. Gresser and J. Shapley, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 2036.

exclusion of this term probably accounts for the observed deviation in the less rigorous Leffler-type of plot (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Plot showing isokinetic relationship for compounds in Table 1. Open circles indicate Leffler type plot and improved fit by solid circles representing plot of $\delta\Delta H^* + 2.303 RT \sigma^+ \rho$ vs. $\delta\Delta S^*$.

Ortho-substituents: The effect of *ortho*-substituents on rates has been extensively studied²⁰, and in general polar effects predominate and tend to reduce the rate of reaction. However, examples are also known where a linear steric energy relationship could be found²¹ for reactions with *ortho*-substituted compounds. Using our rate data at 25° for the hydrolyses of *ortho*-substituted azorhodanines, which are consistently higher (Table 1) than those of the corresponding *para*-derivatives, a fairly linear plot could be discerned in $\log(k/k_0)$ against Taft E_s values²¹ (slope, $\delta = 0.175$). This is somewhat low compared to that ($\delta = 0.301 \pm 0.018$) obtained from alkaline hydrolysis of acetate esters in 70% aqueous dioxane at 30°.²¹

Similarly, decreased stabilities as measured by lower half wave potential, of *ortho*-substituted aromatic compounds, have been reported by Hussey and Diefenderfer²². Results have been explained by the authors by assuming higher electron density at reaction site due to reduced resonance interaction. In our case, spectral data have already indicated²³ the presence of strain in the molecule due to deformation of the lonepair orbital on nitrogen. The net effect is possibly destabilisation of the ground state thereby reducing the steric requirement at the transition state. In this respect, faster rate of hydrolysis of *cis*-*t*-butyl cyclohexyl tosylate²⁴ compared to the *trans*-isomer is a good case in point. Since difference in the transition state for the *ortho*- and *para*-derivatives is minimal, the observed phenomenon may be regarded as "steric assistance" in hydrolyses.

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23. P. B. Talukdar and S. K. Sengupta, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 129.
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